

ON PREDICTING ELASTIC MODULI IN FOAMED METALS USING EQUIVALENT INCLUSION METHOD

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SUMMARY: This study presents a methodology to predict the effective elastic moduli of foamed materials with respect to the variation of voids' volume fraction and void's aspect ratio. The Mori-Tanaka theory is employed to determine the overall stress-strain relation of inclusions embedded in matrix, whether the matrix is isotropic, cubic, or transversely isotropic material. According to our derived results, the overall elastic moduli of a composites are a function of matrix's elastic moduli, inclusion's elastic moduli, inclusion's Eshelby tensor (depends on aspect ratio of the inclusion), and inclusions volume fraction. In addition, the equivalent inclusion method is employed to model the voids of foamed materials as inclusions in which the elastic moduli are nulls. Analysis results indicate that the longitudinal elastic modulus E_{11} , shear moduli G_{12} and G_{13} , and Poisson's ratio ν_{12} for foamed aluminum appear to increase with the increment of void's aspect ratio. Meanwhile, the transverse elastic moduli E_{22} and E_{33} , out-plane shear modulus G_{23} , and Poisson's ratios ν_{21} as well as ν_{23} decrease with increasing aspect ratio of the void. The good coincidence of the numerical results in longitudinal elastic modulus E_{11} with experimental data verifies that the presented methodology has a reliable correctness.

KEYWORDS: foamed metal, Mori-Tanaka Theory, equivalent inclusion method, elastic moduli.

INTRODUCTION

The foamed metals, which have a plurality of random-dispersed voids throughout the metal matrix such as shown in Fig. 1, have received significant attention in applications caused these materials owning versatile advantages. The advantages for foamed metals include acoustic absorption, vibration isolation, low thermal conduction, electricity and magnetism shielding, and fire isolation. The prominent feature that dominates the utilization of these porous materials in structure is how the artificial voids degrade the strength and stiffness of the materials. Thereby, to make the use of foamed metals, it is imperative that the micromechanical characteristics of these materials should be carefully investigated and relevantly incorporated the findings into design methodologies.

Gent and Thomas [1] developed the theory of form mechanics, which assumed the displacements of the junctions inside the bulk of the form are affine. Gibson et al. [2, 3] analyzed the elastic properties of two-dimensional cellular materials and three-dimensional polymeric foams. The elastic properties of the cellular materials were demonstrated by employing a beam subjected to bending, elastic buckling, and plastic collapse. Abeyaratne and Triantafyllidis [4] studied the overall behavior of a highly porous elastic material at finite strains for embracing homogenization theory. Warren and Kraynik [5,6] established a theoretical study for evaluating the linear elastic properties of two-dimensional forms with non-uniform film thickness. They also developed the elastic constants of three-dimensional open-cell foams as functions of compliances for bending and tension of a strut. Ramakrishnan and Arunachalam [7] developed the analytical model, which based on the principal of statistical continuum mechanics and the variation of the effective Poisson's ratio, to determine the effective elastic moduli of porous solids with pores distributed randomly.

Rice [8] studied the porosity-dependent properties of idealized pore structural materials by employing the minimum solid area models.

Recently research featuring the theoretical framework to study the mechanical properties of the porous material, solely, directed toward the consideration of voids volume fraction. Nevertheless, the avoidance of the void shape for porous material for porous material may misjudge the physical properties, especially when the aspect ratio value of void is less than one, such as the void being the tablet spherical shape. Meanwhile, the effect that the aspect ratio value of a fiber is less than one rarely studied on the composite material field. The reason is that the aspect ratio of a reinforced fiber embedded in composite material is commonly larger than one, and in such case the aspect ratio almost no significant domination in the transverse elastic moduli, shear moduli, and Poisson's ratios of composite material. Evidently, it will be impertinent by employing the existing methodologies to study the foamed material with the void aspect ratio ranging from less than one up to greater than one.

In this study, we present a methodology to determine the effective elastic moduli of foamed materials for the void aspect ratio ranging from less than one up to greater than one. Initially, the Mori-Tanaka theory is employed to investigate the overall stress-strain relation of a fibrous composite material. The effective stiffness tensor of a composite then denotes as a function of matrix's elastic moduli, inclusions' elastic moduli, inclusion's Eshelby tensor, and inclusions volume fraction. Utilizing the equivalent inclusion method allows us to model the voids of porous materials as inclusions in which consist of fictitious eigenstrains. The corresponding Eshelby tensors for the voids embedded in distinct matrices with the variation of aspect ratio are presented. In light of the results presented in the work, the effect elastic moduli of foamed aluminum are explicitly obtained with the variation of void's aspect ratio and porosity. The acceptable correspondence of the numerical results in longitudinal elastic modulus E_{11} with experimental data reveals that the presented methodology on predicting effective elastic moduli of foamed materials owns an available exactitude.

Overall Stress-Strain Relation

The overall stress-strain relation of a foamed metal composite is to be investigated by using the method of Huang [9]. This method yields the same effective elastic moduli for the cases when either a stress or a strain is prescribed on the boundary of the composite. Consider a sufficiently large of foamed metal composite D consists of N identically shaped, randomly distributed, and uniformly oriented inhomogeneities $\Omega = \sum_{k=1}^N \Omega_k$ with elastic constants c_{ijmn}^* and volume fraction f . The surrounding matrix is denoted by $D - \Omega$ and has elastic constants c_{ijmn} . In this work, the shape of inhomogeneities is modeled as an ellipsoid defined by

$$\Omega: \frac{x_1^2}{a_1^2} + \frac{x_2^2}{a_2^2} + \frac{x_3^2}{a_3^2} \leq 1, \quad (1)$$

where a_1 , a_2 , and a_3 are the semiaxes of the ellipsoid. The assumption that the shape of inhomogeneities is ellipsoidal enables one to treat composite reinforcement geometries ranging from thin flake to continuous fiber reinforcement.

When the composite is subjected to a surface displacement u_m^0 or far-field applied strains ϵ_{mn}^0 , the disturbed strains due to the presence of the k th inhomogeneity result in each Ω_k . The volume average of the disturbed strains must vanish which yields

$$(1-f)\langle \epsilon_{mn}^M \rangle + f\langle \epsilon_{mn}^\Omega \rangle = 0, \quad (2)$$

where $\langle \epsilon_{mn}^M \rangle$ and $\langle \epsilon_{mn}^\Omega \rangle$ represent the average strains in the matrix and the inhomogeneities, respectively. Then the average stresses in the k^{th} inhomogeneity Ω_k are

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{ij}^0 + \langle \sigma_{ij}^{\Omega_k} \rangle &= C_{ijmn}^* \{ \varepsilon_{mn}^0 + \langle \varepsilon_{mn}^{\Omega_k} \rangle \} \\ &= C_{ijmn}^* \{ \varepsilon_{mn}^0 + \langle \varepsilon_{mn}^M \rangle + \varepsilon_{mn} \} \end{aligned} \quad \text{in } \Omega_k, \quad (3)$$

where ε_{mn} stands for the average disturbed strain due to the existence of the k th inhomogeneity. Since all inhomogeneities are of the same shape with the same material properties, the average value over Ω_k is identical with that over all inhomogeneities, namely, $\sigma_{ij}^0 + \langle \sigma_{ij}^{\Omega_k} \rangle = \sigma_{ij}^0 + \langle \sigma_{ij}^{\Omega} \rangle$.

Utilizing the equivalent inclusion method, the stresses in the inhomogeneities can be simulated by those in the equivalent inclusions with the elastic constants of the matrix and a fictitious eigenstrain, $\varepsilon_{mn}^{*(k)}$. Therefore, equation (3) is written as

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{ij}^0 + \langle \sigma_{ij}^{\Omega} \rangle &= C_{ijmn}^* \{ \varepsilon_{mn}^0 + \langle \varepsilon_{mn}^M \rangle + \varepsilon_{mn} \} \\ &= C_{ijmn} \{ \varepsilon_{mn}^0 + \langle \varepsilon_{mn}^M \rangle + \varepsilon_{mn} - \varepsilon_{mn}^* \}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

This perturbed strains can be related to the fictitious eigenstrain by [10]

$$\varepsilon_{mn} = \frac{1}{8\pi} C_{ijab} \int_{-1}^1 \int_0^{2\pi} \{ N_{mj}(\bar{\xi}) \bar{\xi}_i \bar{\xi}_n + N_{mj}(\bar{\xi}) \bar{\xi}_i \bar{\xi}_n \} D^{-1}(\bar{\xi}) \varepsilon_{ab}^*(\bar{\xi}) d\theta d\bar{\xi}_3, \quad (5)$$

where $N_{mj}(\bar{x})$ and $D(\bar{x})$ are the cofactor and the determinant of the 3×3 matrix $c_{imjn} x_i x_n$ respectively, and

$$\begin{aligned}a_1 \bar{\xi}_1 &= \zeta_1, & a_2 \bar{\xi}_2 &= \zeta_2, & a_3 \bar{\xi}_3 &= \zeta_3, \\ \zeta_1/\zeta &= \bar{\zeta}_1, & \zeta_2/\zeta &= \bar{\zeta}_2, & \zeta_3/\zeta &= \bar{\zeta}_3, & \zeta &= (\zeta_1^2 + \zeta_2^2 + \zeta_3^2)^{1/2}, \\ \bar{\zeta}_1 &= (1 - \bar{\zeta}_3^2)^{1/2} \cos \theta, & \bar{\zeta}_2 &= (1 - \bar{\zeta}_3^2)^{1/2} \sin \theta, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Note that $N_{mj}(\bar{x}) = N_{mj}(\bar{x})$ due to the symmetry of the elastic moduli $c_{imjn} \bar{x}_i \bar{x}_n$. Since all inhomogeneities have an ellipsoidal shape and the applied load is uniform, the equivalent eigenstrains ε_{ab}^* are uniform and thus equation (5) can be written as

$$\varepsilon_{mn} = S_{mnab} \varepsilon_{ab}^*, \quad (7)$$

where

$$S_{mnab} = \frac{1}{8\pi} C_{ijab} \int_{-1}^1 \int_0^{2\pi} \{ N_{mj}(\bar{\xi}) \bar{\xi}_i \bar{\xi}_n + N_{mj}(\bar{\xi}) \bar{\xi}_i \bar{\xi}_n \} D^{-1}(\bar{\xi}) d\theta d\bar{\xi}_3$$

is the well-known Eshelby tensor that is a function of the geometry of inhomogeneities and the material properties of the surrounding matrix. Then, from equation (4), the average strains in each inhomogeneity are given as

$$\begin{aligned}\langle \varepsilon_{mn}^{\Omega} \rangle &= \langle \varepsilon_{mn}^M \rangle + \varepsilon_{mn} \\ &= -f(S_{mnab} - I_{mnab}) \varepsilon_{ab}^* + S_{mnab} \varepsilon_{ab}^*. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The average strains in the matrix are obtained by substituting equation (8) into (2) as

$$\langle \varepsilon_{mn}^M \rangle = -f S_{mnab} \varepsilon_{ab}^*, \quad (9)$$

And the corresponding average stresses are

$$\langle \sigma_{ij}^M \rangle = -f C_{ijmn} S_{mnab} \varepsilon_{ab}^*. \quad (10)$$

To solve for the equivalent eigenstrains $\epsilon_{mn}^{*(k)}$, equation (9) is substituted into the equivalency equation (4), which can then be expressed as

$$\epsilon_{ab}^* = -T_{abij}^{-1} (C_{ijmn}^* - C_{ijmn}) \epsilon_{mn}^0, \quad (11)$$

where T_{abij}^{-1} is the inverse of T_{ijab} defined by

$$T_{ijab} = (I - f)(C_{ijmn}^* - C_{ijmn}) S_{mnab} + C_{ijab}. \quad (12)$$

The overall stresses, $\langle \sigma_{ij}^C \rangle$, of the composite are defined as

$$\langle \sigma_{ij}^C \rangle = \frac{I}{V} \left[\int_{D-\Omega} (\sigma_{ij}^0 + \sigma_{ij}^M) d\mathbf{x} + \int_{\Omega} (\sigma_{ij}^0 + \sigma_{ij}^\Omega) d\mathbf{x} \right]. \quad (13)$$

Substituting equation (10) into (13), followed by some manipulation yields

$$\langle \sigma_{ij}^C \rangle = C_{ijmn} (\epsilon_{mn}^0 - f \epsilon_{mn}^*). \quad (14)$$

Furthermore, several steps of straightforward manipulation after substitution of equation (11) into (14) result in

$$\langle \sigma_{ij}^C \rangle = \bar{C}_{ijmn} \epsilon_{mn}^0, \quad (15)$$

Where the effective stiffness tensor \bar{C}_{ijmn} is defined by

$$\bar{C}_{ijmn} = C_{ijab} \{ I_{abmn} + f T_{abqr}^{-1} (C_{qrmn}^* - C_{qrmn}) \}. \quad (16)$$

The Eshelby tensor in equation (7) may be determined by employing numerical integration for different type of matrix and distinct shape of inclusion. Figures 2 is the Eshelby values for aluminum, with short inclusion under the variation of aspect ratio. The elastic properties of the aluminum matrix in the numerical demonstration, herein, are as follows.

Aluminum (cubic material):

$$C_{11}=C_{22}=C_{33}=108.25(\text{GPa}), C_{12}=C_{13}=C_{23}=61.29(\text{GPa}), C_{44}=C_{55}=C_{66}=28.47(\text{GPa}).$$

Elastic Moduli of Foamed Aluminum

Foamed aluminum, which contains voids, is a porous material, the voids may consider as short inclusions with the elastic constants c_{ijmn}^* being null. After substitution of the Eshelby values in equation (7) into equations (12) and (16), the effective stiffness tensor c_{ijmn} then acquires for foamed aluminum with voids volume fraction f . Furthermore, by employing the relation between stiffness constants and effect elastic moduli, the elastic moduli of foamed aluminum may be obtained. The relation between stiffness constants and effect elastic moduli for the foamed aluminum can be denoted as follows.

$$\bar{C}_{11} = \frac{1 - (v_{23})^2}{(E_{22})^2 \Delta}$$

$$\bar{C}_{12} = \frac{\nu_{21} + \nu_{21}\nu_{23}}{(E_{22})^2 \Delta}$$

$$\bar{C}_{13} = \frac{\nu_{21} + \nu_{21}\nu_{23}}{(E_{22})^2 \Delta}$$

$$\bar{C}_{22} = \frac{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}{E_{11}E_{22}\Delta}$$

$$\bar{C}_{23} = \frac{\nu_{23} + \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}{E_{11}E_{22}\Delta} \quad (17)$$

$$\bar{C}_{33} = \frac{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}{E_{11}E_{22}\Delta}$$

$$\bar{C}_{44} = G_{23}$$

$$\bar{C}_{55} = G_{13}$$

$$\bar{C}_{66} = G_{12}$$

$$\text{where } \Delta = \frac{1 - 2\nu_{12} - (\nu_{23})^2 - 2\nu_{21}\nu_{23}\nu_{12}}{E_{11}(E_{22})^2}$$

$$\text{bulk modulus } k = \frac{E}{3(1 - 2\nu)}$$

According to the numerical results, Figure 3 depicts how the aspect ratio of the void influences the longitudinal elastic modulus E_{11} of foamed aluminum under the variation of voids volume fraction. This figure also indicates that the longitudinal elastic modulus E_{11} for every void aspect ratio monotonously decreases with respect to the extension of voids volume fraction and lower aspect ratio has lower elastic modulus. Notably, when the void aspect ratio is one means the void shape is spherical. Figure 4 reveals that the values of transverse elastic moduli E_{22} and E_{33} also monotonously decrease with the increasing of voids volume fraction, but lower aspect ratio owns higher elastic modulus. Fig. 4 indicates that the mutual values of E_{22} have no apparent change when aspect ratios are greater than one, this fact also verifies that the macro-mechanical composites theory can disregard the influence of aspect ratio to transverse elastic modulus only in aspect ratio bigger than one. Based on the results of Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, the values of E_{11} , E_{22} , and E_{33} are the same for foamed aluminum when the void aspect ratio is one. Fig. 3 and Fig 4 also exhibits a rational trend of E_{11} , E_{22} , and E_{33} converging to the value, zero, when total porosity is approached.

Figure 5 displays the increment of voids volume fraction on shear moduli G_{12} and G_{13} with the variation of void aspect ratio. According to this figure, it is no apparently difference for aspect ratio values above one. The shear modulus G_{23} with respect to the increment of voids volume fraction are shown in Fig. 6. In Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, they also reveal the zero value convergence when total porosity is approached.

The Poisson's ratios ν_{12} , ν_{21} and ν_{23} with respect to the variation of void's aspect ratio and voids volume fraction depict in Fig. 7, 8, and 9, respectively. In Figure 7, the Poisson's

ratio ν_{12} has apparent decreasing with the increment of voids volume fraction when aspect ratio is 0.2, while the Poisson's ratio value becomes proportional increment with voids volume fraction at the condition of aspect ratio above 3.4. Figure 9 shows that the values of the Poisson's ratio ν_{23} also monotonously decrease with the increasing of voids volume fraction, provided lower aspect ratio owns higher values of the Poisson's ratio. Figure 10 exposes the comparison of the numerical simulation for embracing the presented methodology and experimental results acquired from Otsuka [13] in the elastic modulus E_{11} for the foamed aluminum. The numerical results with void's aspect ratio being 0.2 have a fair conformity with experimental data.

Conclusions

This work presents a methodology to predict the effective elastic moduli of foamed materials with respect to the variation of void's volume fraction and aspect ratio. The Mori-Tanaka theory method is employed to determine the overall stress-strain relation of a composite material. In addition, the equivalent inclusion method is employed to model the voids of foamed materials as inclusions in which the overall elastic moduli are nulls. According to our results, the overall elastic moduli of a foamed material are a function of matrix's elastic moduli, void's aspect ratio, and voids volume fraction. Analysis results indicate that the longitudinal elastic modulus E_{11} , shear moduli G_{12} and G_{13} , and Poisson's ratio ν_{12} for foamed aluminum appear to increase with the increment of void's aspect ratio. The good correspondence of the numerical results in longitudinal elastic modulus E_{11} with experimental data verifies that the presented methodology on predicting elastic moduli of foamed materials has an available accuracy.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank the National Science Council of the Republic of China for financially supporting this research under contract Nos. NSC 87-2623-D-035-005 and NSC 87-2216-E-035-016.

Figure 1. Photograph of a foamed aluminum plate

Figure 2. The effect of aspect ratio in Eshelby tensor for cylindrical inclusion ($a_3/a_2=1$) in the isotropic matrix epoxy.

Figure 3. The variation of voids' volume fraction and aspect ratio on elastic modulus E_{11} .

Figure 4. The variation of voids' volume fraction and aspect ratio on elastic modulus E_{22} and E_{33} .

Figure 5. The variation of voids' volume fraction and aspect ratio on shear elastic modulus G_{12} and G_{13} .

Figure 6. The variation of voids' volume fraction and aspect ratio on shear modulus G_{23} .

Figure 7. The variation of voids' volume fraction and aspect ratio on Poisson ratio η_{12} .

Figure 8. The variation of voids' volume fraction and aspect ratio on Poisson ratio η_{21} .

Figure 9. The variation of voids' volume fraction and aspect ratio on Poisson's ratio η_{23} .

Fig. 10 The comparison of the numerical simulation and experimental results acquired from Otsuka [12] in the elastic modulus E_{11} for the formed aluminum.

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